

2nd European Congress of Health Sciences

May 4-5, 2024 - Bristow, VA / USA (ONLINE)
medjeur.com/congress

Oral Presentation-16

doi: 10.5281/zenodo.11085029

Evaluation of the Effect of Compassion Fatigue on Brain Fog Level in Hemodialysis Healthcare Professionals

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Introduction and Aim

The long-term intense compassion and sympathy shown by individuals with high levels of empathy may be replaced by "compassion fatigue". Individual with compassion fatigue may feel helpless, confused, have difficulty in focusing and multitasking. The mental fatigue and confusion experienced by individuals with compassion fatigue can lead to many symptoms referred to as "brain fog". Brain fog represents psychobiological and behavioral conditions caused by prolonged and challenging cognitive activities.

When the literature is examined, it is stated that compassion fatigue is seen in healthcare professionals in pediatrics, emergency, intensive care, oncology, dialysis and palliative care units. However, no study has examined the effects of brain fog caused by compassion fatigue in healthcare professionals in hemodialysis units.

The aim of this study is to determine the level of compassion fatigue and brain fog in healthcare professionals in hemodialysis units and to reveal the relationship between compassion fatigue and brain fog.

Materials and Methods

The population of this study includes healthcare professionals in public and private hemodialysis centers in Turkey. 440 volunteers who have provided the research criteria have participated in the study. Data collection tools are "Introductory Information Form", "Compassion Fatigue Scale" and "Brain Fog Scale". The compassion fatigue scale is 10-point Likert type and consists of 13 questions. The brain fog scale is a five-point Likert type and consists of 30 questions. Data were collected via Google Form between February 16 and April 16, 2024. The study was sensitive to ethical principles. Informed consents of volunteers were obtained electronically. Approval was also obtained from a local ethics committee.

IBM SPSS 24 package program was used to analyze the data. The suitability of the data for normal distribution was evaluated with Shapiro Wilk's test and skewness-kurtosis values. Continuous data are given as mean \pm standard deviation, categorical data as n and %. Independent sample t test was used to compare normally distributed scale scores in terms of two-group variables. One Way Anova test was used to compare data containing more than two groups. Pearson correlation test was performed to compare the relationship between the scores of the Compassion Fatigue Scale and the Brain Fog Scale. In all analyses, the significance level was evaluated as 0.05 and the confidence interval (CI) was 95%.

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Results

Table 1. Distribution of Compassion Fatigue Scale Scores According to Participants' Sociodemographic and Professional Characteristics

	Total n(%)	Secondary Trauma		Professional Burnout		Scale Scores	
		Mean(SD)	p	Mean(SD)	p	Mean(SD)	p
Gender							
Famale	361 (82.0)	24,09(10.67)	0.192	37,41(16.34)	0.556	61,50(25.16)	0.351
Male	79(18.0)	22,36(10.46)		36,21(16.42)		58,58(25.39)	
Total	440(100.0)	23.78(10.64)		37.19(16.34)		60.98(25.20)	
Educational Status							
High school	20(4.5)	19,35(10.54)	0.131	31,40(17.23)	0.227	50,75(25.57)	0.248
Associate's degree	119(27.0)	24,44(11.77)		39,32(17.49)		63,77(27.19)	
Licence	251(57.0)	24,27(10.23)		36,70(16.05)		60,98(24.79)	
Master's degree	38(8.6)	21,02(9.29)		38,13(13.74)		59,15(21.01)	
PhD	12(2.7)	23.0(9.82)		33,08(15.44)		56,08(22.70)	
Marital status							
Married	317(72.0)	23.86(10.31)	0,792	36.68(16.04)	0,294	60.55(24.45)	0,569
Single	123(28.0)	23.56(11.49)		38.51(17.11)		62.08(27.10)	
Occupation							
Nurse	232(52.7)	23.53(10.19)	0,015 difference: 2-4 3-2,4	36.13(15.17)	0,005 difference: 3-1,2,4	59.67(21.25)	0,004 difference: 3-1,2,4
Doctor	23(5.2)	19.08(9.27)		31.13(13.77)		50.21(21.30)	
Dialysis Technician	174(39.5)	25.09(11.06)		40.00(16.86)		65.10(25.94)	
Support Personnel	11(2.5)	18.090(12.18)		27.81(17.41)		45.90(28.18)	
Institution							
Public	343(78.0)	23.66(10.33)	0,667	37.09(16.24)	0,796	60.75(24.80)	0,727
Private	97(22.0)	24.19(11.69)		37.57(16.78)		61.77(26.67)	
Years of Working in the Profession							
1-5 years	99(22.5)	23,65(11.60)	0,206	38,75(17.32)	0,168	62,41(27.40)	0,173
6-10 years	54(12.3)	22,59(11.90)		37,22(17.24)		59,81(27.04)	
11-15 years	74(16.8)	26,33(9.40)		40,16(15.51)		66,50(23.25)	
16-20 years	64(14.5)	24.00(10.85)		36,79(16.65)		60,79(24.99)	
>21 years	149(33.9)	22,93(9.88)		34,85(15.46)		57,79(23.76)	
Years of Working in the Hemodialysis Unit							
1-5 years	134(30.5)	24,11(11.31)	0,971	38,86(17.26)	0,642	62,97(27.05)	0,824
6-10 years	79(18.0)	23,88(11.68)		37,06(15.55)		60,94(25.32)	
11-15 years	82(18.6)	23,37(8.59)		37,12(16.06)		60,50(22.84)	
16-20 years	61(13.9)	24,18(11.42)		36,01(16.69)		60,19(25.53)	
>21 years	84(19.1)	23,27(9.92)		35,59(15.72)		58,86(24.30)	
Age range							
18-25 years	61(13.9)	23,11(12.01)	0,102	38,86(17.35)	0,136	61,98(27.79)	0,105
26-35 years	132(30.0)	24,76(10.53)		38,86(16.21)		63,62(24.65)	
36-45 years	148(33.6)	24,37(10.63)		37,07(16.67)		61,44(25.57)	
46-55 years	90(20.5)	22,61(9.69)		34,76(15.37)		57,37(23.51)	
>56 years	9(2.0)	16.00(9.05)		27,77(11.48)		43,77(18.05)	

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The distribution of the participants according to their socio-demographic and professional characteristics is given in Table 1. 82.0% of the healthcare professionals participating in the study are women, 57.0% have a bachelor's degree, 72.0% are married, 52.7% are nurses, and 39.5% are dialysis technicians. 30.0% of the individuals are between the ages of 26-35 and 33.6% are between the ages of 36-45. When professional characteristics were examined, it was seen that the total working years of 22.5% were 1-5 years, and 33.9% were 21 or more years. It was determined that 30.5% of the working time in the hemodialysis unit was 1-5 years, and 19.1% was 21 or more years.

When the distribution of compassion fatigue short scale scores according to the participants' socio-demographic and professional characteristics was examined, it was seen that the compassion fatigue scale scores differed significantly according to the participants' professional status. When nurses' compassion fatigue scale scores are examined; It was observed that the mean score of the secondary trauma subscale was 23.53 (10.19), the mean score of the professional burnout subscale was 36.13 (15.17), and the mean total score of the compassion fatigue scale was 59.67 (21.25). It was observed that the secondary trauma, professional burnout subscales and compassion fatigue scale total scores of dialysis technicians were significantly higher than other employees (Table 1).

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Table 2. Distribution of Brain Fog Scale Scores According to Participants' Sociodemographic and Occupational Characteristics

	Cognitive Symptoms		Physical Symptoms		Psychological Symptoms		Scale Scores	
	Mean(SD)	p	Mean(SD)	p	Mean(SD)	p	Mean(SD)	p
Gender								
Famale	43,21(16.05)	0,844	23,80(8.30)	0,404	13,60(5.86)	0,864	80,62(27.60)	0,863
Male	43,60(16.05)		22,93(8.41)		13,48(5.43)		80,02(28.40)	
Educational Status								
High school	36,30(15.82)	0,274	23,10(7.53)	0,025	11,05(5.29)	0,109	70,45(26.04)	0,254
Associate's degree	43,63(18.07)		25,78(8.57)	differe nce:	14,40(6.06)		83,82(30.16)	
Licence	44,02(15.28)		22,96(8.35)	1-2,	13,46(5.67)		80,45(27.07)	
Master's degree	42,05(13.72)		22,23(6.78)	2-3,	13,68(5.53)		77,97(23.77)	
PhD	39,91(16.40)		22,16(7.95)	3-4	11,75(5.65)		73,83(28.12)	
Marital status								
Married	42,88(15.36)	0,428	23,22(7.96)	0,106	13,38(5.64)	0,252	79,48(26.67)	0,240
Single	44,32(17.68)		24,73(9.10)		14,08(6.10)		83,15(30.19)	
Occupation								
Nurse	43,19(15.05)	0,042	23,25(8.19)	0,001	13,56(5.74)	0,039	80,01(26.53)	0,008
Doctor	36,52(12.53)	differe nce:	18,65(6.81)	differe nce:	10,65(4.53)	differe nce:	65,82(22.15)	differe nce:
Dialysis Technician	44,79(17.37)	2-3	25,05(8.36)	1-2,3	14,10(5.84)	1-2,	83,94(29.05)	1-2, 2-3
Support Personnel	35,54(16.77)		20,00(7.94)	2-3, 3-4	11,81(6.47)	2-3	67,36(29.85)	
Institution								
Public	44,15(15.75)	0,033	23,67(8.27)	0,884	13,65(5.76)	0,627	81,48(27.32)	0,168
Private	40,21(16.74)		23,53(8.53)		13,32(5.86)		77,08(28.95)	
Years of Working in the Profession								
1-5 years	43,36(16.97)	0,013	25,60(9.41)	< 0,001	14,12(6.36)	0,210	83,09(30.06)	0,007
6-10 years	43,94(18.24)	differe nce:	23,77(7.63)	differe nce:	13,33(5.87)	differe nce:	81,05(28.92)	differe nce:
11-15 years	48,66(15.89)	1-3,	25,89(7.16)	1-4,5,	14,54(5.41)	3-5	89,09(26.04)	1-5,
16-20 years	42,57(16.36)	3-4,5	22,65(8.29)	3-2,5	13,70(5.83)		78,93(28.39)	3-4, 3-5
>21 years	40,63(13.88)		21,60(7.83)		12,78(5.44)		75,02(25.11)	
Years of Working in the Hemodialysis Unit								
1-5 years	44,63(17.52)	0,440	25,50(9.29)	0,005	14,52(6.38)	0,250	84,66(30.59)	0,142
6-10 years	44,29(15.98)		24,10(7.38)	differe nce:	13,20(5.04)		81,59(25.91)	
11-15 years	43,71(15.31)		23,57(7.17)	1-3,4,5	13,10(5.22)		80,40(25.56)	
16-20 years	41,77(14.83)		22,03(7.92)	1-5	13,42(5.91)		77,22(26.39)	
>21 years	40,86(15.12)		21,50(8.26)		13,00(5.78)		75,36(26.99)	
Age range								
18-25 years	40,49(17.02)	0,001	25,44(9.23)	< 0,001	14,19(6.29)	0,103	80,13(30.31)	0,001
26-35 years	47,81(16.72)	differe nce:	25,64(8.07)	differe nce:	14,15(5.95)	differe nce:	87,60(27.63)	differe nce:
36-45 years	42,39(15.81)	1-2,	22,43(8.20)	1-3,4,5	13,38(5.59)	1-5,	78,21(27.79)	2-3,4,5
46-55 years	41,21(13.64)	2,	22,33(7.42)	2-3,4,5	13,07(5.48)	2-5,	76,62(24.22)	3-5
>56 years	31,33(8.87)	2-3,4,5	15,11(4.62)	3-5, 4-5	9,33(3.70)	3-5	55,77(15.95)	

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The distribution of brain fog scale scores according to the socio-demographic and professional characteristics of the participants is given in Table 2. It was determined that the brain fog scale sub-dimension or total scores differed significantly depending on the individuals' educational level, profession, institution of employment, length of time working in the profession-hemodialysis, and age range. When the average scores of the nurses on the brain fog scale are examined; It was observed that the cognitive symptoms sub-dimension was 43.19 (15.05), the physical symptoms sub-dimension was 23.25 (8.19), the psychological symptoms sub-dimension was 13.56 (5.74), and the brain fog scale total score was 80.01 (26.53). It was observed that the brain fog scale sub-dimension or total score averages of those working in the public sector, those with a total working period of 1-5 years in occupational hemodialysis, and those aged 26-35 were significantly higher than the other groups.

Table 3. Correlation Between the Compassion Fatigue Scale and the Brain Fog Scale

		Secondary Trauma	Professional Burnout	Compassion Fatigue Scale-Scores
Cognitive Symptoms	r	,597**	,632**	,662**
	p	<.001	<.001	<.001
Physical Symptoms	r	,584**	,710**	,707**
	p	<.001	<.001	<.001
Psychological Symptoms	r	,568**	,728**	,712**
	p	<.001	<.001	<.001
Brain Fog Scale-total	r	,639**	,730**	,744**
	p	<.001	<.001	<.001

** p<.001

The Correlation Between the Compassion Fatigue Scale and the Brain Fog Scale is given in Table 3. It was determined that there was a positive, high-level, significant relationship between the compassion fatigue scale sub-dimension and total scores and the brain fog scale sub-dimension and total scores.

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Conclusion

In our study, it was determined that the compassion fatigue and brain fog scores of healthcare professionals were at moderate levels. It was determined that compassion fatigue total scores and subdimension scores differ according to occupational groups. It was determined that brain fog total scores differed depending on variables such as occupational groups, working year and age range. A positive relationship has been found between compassion fatigue and brain fog.

In line with our study results; It may be recommended for employers to improve the working conditions of healthcare personnel, increase their motivation, and provide biopsychosocial support. In order to draw attention to this issue, researchers may be advised to work with larger samples. Training can be organized to ensure conscious awareness for healthcare professionals, and compassion fatigue and brain fog conditions of healthcare professionals can be evaluated periodically.

Keywords: Brain fog, Compassion fatigue, Dialysis, Health, Healthcare professionals, Hemodialysis.

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